

Oxidimetric Determination of Ascorbic Acid using Potassium Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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Ascorbic acid is determined titrimetrically using potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) as oxidimetric reagent in 12-14*M* acetic acid and 0.4-1.5*M* sulphuric acid medium. Diphenylamine is used as indicator in the visual titration. The formal potentials for ferricyanide/ferrocyanide system in the above medium are determined. The present procedure tolerates, to a fairly large extent, the presence of several organic compounds likely to be associated with ascorbic acid in plant tissues.

POTASSIUM hexacyanoferrate(III) is described as a one equivalent electron abstracting reagent¹ and is used for the determination of many organic compounds. Several earlier workers²⁻⁸ determined ascorbic acid using potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), among them Erdey et al⁹ reported an error of -1.67 to +3.80 in their automatic microtitration and Weisner et al¹⁰ reported an error of 2-3% in an indirect determination.

The detection and determination of diphenylamine in 11-14 *M* acetic acid and 0.5-1.5 *M* sulphuric acid medium using potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) has been reported by us¹¹. This led us to take up the oxidation of ascorbic acid using diphenylamine as indicator in the above medium.

Experimental

0.1 *M* solution of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) (B.D.H. AnalaR) was prepared by weighing and standardised iodometrically¹². 0.05 *M* solution of ascorbic acid (G. R. SMC) was prepared by weighing and standardised according to Ballentine's procedure¹³. 0.01 *M* solution of diphenylamine (E. Merck) was prepared in glacial acetic acid (Selectipur, Merck). All other chemicals are of analytical reagent grade quality.

Visual Titration :

70 ml of glacial acetic acid (12 *M* overall), 10 ml of sulphuric acid of 5 *M* (0.5 *M* overall), 1.0 ml diphenylamine and an aliquot of ascorbic acid are taken in an Erlenmeyer flask such that the total volume at end point is kept at 100 ml, and titrated against standard potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) solution. The end point is heralded by the distinct colour change from colourless to bluish-violet colour which is stable for at least an hour. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VISUAL TITRATION OF ASCORBIC ACID vs POTASSIUM HEXACYANOFERRATE(III)
FERRICYANIDE : 0.1118*M*; ASCORBIC ACID : 0.04915*M*

Sl. No.	Amount of ascorbic acid taken mg	Amount of ascorbic acid found mg	Standard Deviation
1	86.56	89.19	
2	86.56	89.02	
3	86.56	89.37	0.15
4	77.91	80.34	
5	73.58	75.80	
6	43.28	44.62	

Potentiometric Titration :

70 ml of glacial acetic acid (12 *M* overall), 10 ml of sulphuric acid of 5 *M* (0.5 *M* overall) are taken in a 150 ml beaker ; 1.0 ml of diphenylamine and an aliquot of ascorbic acid are added. The total volume of the solution is kept at 100 ml at the end point. Titration is carried out with potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) using bright platinum electrode as the indicator electrode and saturated calomel electrode as reference one, and ammonium nitrate salt bridge (sintered disc type). Steady potentials are obtained during titration within 1 minute well before and after the end point and within 3-4 minutes just around the end point. The results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF ASCORBIC ACID vs POTASSIUM HEXACYANOFERRATE(III)
FERRICYANIDE : 0.1118*M*; ASCORBIC ACID : 0.04915*M*

Sl. No.	Amount of ascorbic acid taken mg	Amount of ascorbic acid found mg	Standard Deviation
1	86.56	86.10	
2	86.56	86.10	
3	86.56	86.60	0.19
4	73.58	73.31	
5	43.28	43.10	
6	60.59	60.42	

Results and Discussion

The potentiometric determination agrees with that of Ballentine's¹³. The formal potentials of ferricyanide/ferrocyanide system increase with increase in the percentage of acetic acid. The formal potential at the conditions recommended in the procedure is 958 mV (at 70% acetic acid medium) against NHE.

In the visual titration a positive error of 3.05 $\pm$ 0.1% (with the standard deviation of 0.15) is observed. However, the potentiometric titration is consistent with the standard method. As such the potentiometric titration of ascorbic acid in the medium recommended along with diphenylamine clearly differentiated the potential break at the theoretical equivalence point and that obtained visually. The titration potential values at the theoretical equivalence point and that at the colour change of the indicator are 816 mV and 886 mV against NHE respectively. The reason may probably be attributed to the E_{high} value of diphenylamine being 0.86 V¹⁴ requiring further 3% excess of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) for its being oxidized. This, therefore, represents the positive error reported in Table 1 and can be construed as the indicator error. Diphenyl benzidine, diphenylamine sulfonic acid, *n*-phenylanthranilic acid are found to be unsatisfactory in this medium, whose E_{high} values¹⁴ are 0.94 V, 0.91 V and 1.0 V respectively.

Order of addition has no effect on either of these determinations. The colour change in the visual procedure is distinct between the concentrations 0.4 to 1.5 M with respect to sulphuric acid and between the concentrations 12-14 M with respect to acetic acid. The effect of use of other acids instead of sulphuric acid has also been studied and found that perchloric acid acts similarly as sulphuric acid and hydrochloric and nitric acids do not give satisfactory colour transition.

Interferences :

A 100-fold excess (concentrationwise) of citric acid, tartaric acid, glucose, phenol, hydrazine sulphate, hydroxylamine hydrochloride do not interfere.

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